

Western Ionian Sea Data Management Plan

Version 1.0

**EMSO ERIC
December 2024**

History of changes

Version	Date	Change	Author(s)
0.1	20/12/2023	First draft	Claudia Fratianni
1.0	18/12/2024	Updated description	Paolo Bagiacchi

Western Ionian Sea — Data Management Plan

Dataset Overview

Dataset Title

Time series of the Western Ionian Sea (WIS) EMSO ERIC Regional Facility.

Dataset Description

WIS seafloor multi-sensor platforms operate at a depth of ~2100 m and collect a wide variety of oceanographic data in real time. The datasets are stored as time series data in JSON files, in some cases using domain-specific formats (WAV, GCF, etc).

Data Collection

Data description

The Western Ionian Sea (WIS) Regional Facility is a cabled multidisciplinary deep-sea observatory located offshore on the eastern coast of Sicily. The multidisciplinary observatory is located in an area characterised by high seismic activity and the presence of Etna Volcano. It is also in a strategic position to study the oceanographic circulation of the Ionian Sea.

Measured parameters (time-series data):

- bottom-water pressure;
- bottom-water temperature;
- subsurface currents;
- bottom-water oxygen;
- bottom-water salinity.

All data are transmitted in real time via an underwater electro-optical cable to a shore station that performs data acquisition and data storage.

Data quality

The time series data are quality controlled, custom scripts are executed to validate the data and avoid spurious and erratic values, including JSON format correctness.

Data format

Distributed datasets follow the EMSO ERIC Data and Metadata Specifications, a superset of OceanSITES specifications, compliant with CF standards, with some additional metadata coming from SeaDataNet specifications, adding meaningful information to the distributed datasets.

Data Policy

Distributed datasets are compliant with FAIR principles and are openly available.

Documentation and Metadata

Metadata are centralized in the MOIST web-portal database and then propagated to ERDDAP. Metadata fields include generic metadata (title, summary, processing level info, owner, coordinates, PI, data curator, time-coverage) and sensor-specific metadata (model, manufacturer, serial number, type of sensor, deployment depth, etc.).

The metadata is also standardised into NetCDF files following the format conventions and standards compliant with EMSO ERIC Metadata Specifications.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

INGV collects datasets and it is the owner. No sensitive data are provided.

Observatory data are licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

Selection and Preservation

INGV manages the preservation of raw data in its infrastructure.

The raw file-based data are acquired by custom scripts and archived in a regular Windows filesystem organized according to an INSTRUMENT/YEAR/MONTH/<hourly files> directory structure.

All datasets are replicated to ensure redundancy in two different data centers, one in Rome and the other in Portopalo di Capo Passero.

Data Sharing

To get access to data, two ways are available: ERDDAP and MOIST web-portal.

Datasets are free and available through the Western Ionian Sea ERDDAP server (<https://erddap.moist.it/erddap/index.html>) and Western Ionian Sea MOIST data portal (http://www.moist.it/sites/western_ionian_sea/2).

Western Ionian Sea observatory data is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

Responsibilities and Resources

The DMP implementation is under the responsibility of Paolo Bagiacchi, with the full support of the INGV team involved in the Western Ionian Sea activities.

The cost of making data FAIR is supported by the Western Ionian Sea.